

Name of the regions labeled in the quail brain atlas	LUT number (Left-Right)	Partonomy describing the brain organization		
		according to the embryonic vesicles	according to the mammalian brain	according to the chick brain atlas
Olfactory bulb	1-101	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
Pallium	2-102	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
Apical hyperpallium	3-103	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
Ventral hyperpallium	4-104	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
		<i>This region includes intermediate and densocellular hyperpallium.</i>		
Hippocampus	5-105	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
Mesopallium	6-106	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
Nidopallium	7-107	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
Auditory parts of the nidopallium	8-108	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
Auditory Field L2	9-109	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
Entopallium	10-110	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
		<i>This region is also named visual nuclei of the nidopallium.</i>		
Anterior amygdala area	11-111	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
Arcopallium-amygdaloid complex	12-112	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
Extended amygdala	13-113	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Subpallium
Amygdaloid taenial area	14-114	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
		<i>This region includes the amygdaloid taenial nucleus and parataenial area of the amygdala</i>		
Basal somatosensory nucleus of the nidopallium	15-115	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
Striatopallidal area	16-116	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Subpallium
Lateral striatum	17-117	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Subpallium
Striatum	18-118	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Subpallium
Accumbens nucleus	19-119	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Subpallium
Bed nucleus of the stria terminalis	20-120	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Subpallium
Nucleus of the diagonal band	21-121	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Subpallium
		<i>This region includes the nucleus of the vertical limb and the nucleus of the horizontal limb of the diagonal band</i>		
Lateral septum	22-122	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Subpallium
Septum	23-123	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Subpallium
Caudocentral septal area	24-124	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Subpallium
Basal nucleus of Meynert	25-125	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Subpallium
Preoptic area	26-126	Forebrain	Diencephalon	Subpallium
Lateral preoptic area	27-127	Forebrain	Diencephalon	Subpallium
Hypothalamus	28-128	Forebrain	Diencephalon	Hypothalamus and secondary prosencephalon
Lateral hypothalamus	29-129	Forebrain	Diencephalon	Hypothalamus and secondary prosencephalon
Thalamus	30-130	Forebrain	Diencephalon	Thalamus
		<i>This region includes the different parts of the thalamus which were not segmented</i>		
Dorsolateral anterior nucleus of the thalamus	31-131	Forebrain	Diencephalon	Thalamus
Dorsomedial anterior nucleus of the thalamus	32-132	Forebrain	Diencephalon	Thalamus

Dorsal paraventricular nucleus of the thalamus	33-133	Forebrain	Diencephalon	Thalamus
Rotundus nucleus	34-134	Forebrain	Diencephalon	Thalamus
Subgeniculate nucleus	35-135	Forebrain	Diencephalon	Prethalamus
Dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus	36-136	Forebrain	Diencephalon	Thalamus
Anterior pretectal and subpretectal nuclei	37-137	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Pretectum
		<i>This region includes all the parts of anterior and intermediate pretectal nuclei.</i>		
Diffuse pretectal area	38-138	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Pretectum
		<i>This region includes the principal pretectal nucleus (also named principal pretectal nucleus of the commissural pretectum).</i>		
Tectal gray	39-139	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Mesencephalon
		<i>This region includes the superficial and the central stratum of the central gray and probably the periventricular stratum.</i>		
Optic tectum	40-140	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Mesencephalon
		This region includes the different layers of the optic tectum (stratum griseum and fibrosum superficiale).		
Periventricular and central stratum	41-141	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Mesencephalon
		<i>This region was delineated according to its contrast, which was darker than its adjacent areas. It includes the stratum griseum periventricular (SPV), a very thin layer in the optic tectum in border of the ventricle, the stratum album centrale (SAC) of the optic tectum, and overlaps the stratum griseum central of the optic tectum because the border with the next layer of the optic tectum was weakly detectable.</i>		
Midbrain vocal area	42-142	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Mesencephalon
Mesencephalic reticular formation	43-143	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Mesencephalon
Preisthmic region of the midbrain	44-144	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Mesencephalon
		<i>This region includes the magnocellular preisthmic nucleus (Puelles et al 2019)</i>		
Isthmic nucleus	45-145	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Isthmus
Dorsal nucleus of the lateral lemniscus	46-146	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Isthmus
Substantia nigra	47-147	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Mesencephalon
		<i>This region includes the reticular and compacta pars of the mesencephalic substantia nigra</i>		
Midbrain	49-149	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Mesencephalon
		<i>This region gathers all the unsegmented brain regions located between the most caudal diencephalic brain regions, such as thalamus, and the hindbrain. In the template the border between the midbrain and the rostral hindbrain was defined by the weak grey level band observed from the dorsal border of the oculomotor nerve and the longitudinal fasciculus</i>		
Dorsal part of the periaqueductal gray	56-156	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Mesencephalon
Medioventral part of the periaqueductal gray	57-157	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Mesencephalon
Accessory oculomotor nuclei	58-158	Midbrain	Mesencephalon	Pretectum
		<i>This region includes the Edinger-Westphal nucleus and the Darkschewitsch nucleus. It is observed ventrally to the medioventral part of the periaqueductal gray and dorsally to the longitudinal fasciculus</i>		
Rostral hindbrain	59-159	Hindbrain	Mesencephalon, Myelencephalon	Rhombencephalon
Semilunar nucleus	60-160	Hindbrain	Mesencephalon, Myelencephalon	Rhombencephalon
Ventral tegmental area	61-161	Hindbrain	Mesencephalon	Isthmus, mesencephalon, pretectum, thalamus, prethalamus, secondary prosencephalon
Ambiguus nucleus	62-162	Hindbrain	Myelencephalon	Rhombencephalon
Caudal hindbrain	71-171	Hindbrain	Myelencephalon	Rhombencephalon

Olivary cochlear area	72-172	Hindbrain	Mesencephalon, Myelencephalon, Pons	Rhombencephalon
Lateral pontine nucleus	73-173	Hindbrain	Pons	Rhombencephalon
Olfactory tract	201-301	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
		<i>This region includes the medial, lateral and ventral olfactory tracts.</i>		
Unknown rostralateral band	202-302	Forebrain	Telencephalon	
		<i>This region was darker than the adjacent areas with a shape of diagonal band. This part was not identified in the chick brain atlas</i>		
Corticomesencephalic tract	203-303			Pallium
		<i>This tract was also named septopalliomesencephalic tract</i>		
Frontoamygdaloïd tract	204-304	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Pallium
Amygdalohypothalamic tract	205-305	Forebrain	Telencephalon, Diencephalon	Pallium
Amygdalofugal tract	206-306			Pallium
Lateral forebrain bundle	207-307			Pallium
Medial forebrain bundle	208-308			Pallium
Optic tract	209-309			Subthalamus, secondary prosencephalon
Nigrostriatal tract	210-310			Pallium
Quintofrontal tract	211-311			Pallium
Oculomotor nerve	212-312			Mesencephalon
Tectopretectal tract	213-313			Mesencephalon
Tectothalamic tract	214-314			Mesencephalon
Tectotegmental tract	215-315			Mesencephalon
Isthmotectal tract	216-316			Isthmus
Isthmooptic tract	217-317			Isthmus
Tectotegmental decussation	218-318			Mesencephalon
		<i>This region includes the dorsal and ventral parts of the tectotegmental decussation.</i>		
Medial longitudinal fasciculus	219-319			Rhombencephalon
Lobule 1 of the cerebellum (Cb)	501-531			Cerebellum
Lobule 2 of the Cb	502-532			Cerebellum
Lobule 3 of the Cb	503-533			Cerebellum
Lobule 4 of the Cb	504-534			Cerebellum
Lobule 5 of the Cb	505-535			Cerebellum
Lobule 6 of the Cb	506-536			Cerebellum
Lobule 7 of the Cb	507-537			Cerebellum
Lobule 8 of the Cb	508-538			Cerebellum
Lobule 9 of the Cb	509-539			Cerebellum
Lobule 10 of the Cb	510-540			Cerebellum
Medial cerebellum nucleus	511-541			Cerebellum
Lateral cerebellum nucleus	512-542			Cerebellum
Cerebellar white matter	525-555			Cerebellum
Cerebellar peduncles	526-556			Cerebellum
Mammillary bodies	48	Forebrain	Diencephalon	Secondary prosencephalon
Optic chiasm	401	Forebrain	Diencephalon	Secondary prosencephalon
Hippocampal commissure	402	Forebrain	Telencephalon	Subpallium
		Forebrain	Telencephalon	Secondary prosencephalon

The extern lateral limits of the region were differently defined according to the literature. In Poissenot et al. (2019), the lateral borders were defined as the occipitomesencephalicus tract whereas there were included in the anterior commissure for Puelles et al. (2019).

Supraoptic decussation	404	Forebrain	Diencephalon	Subpallium
Posterior commissure	405			Pretectum
Vestibular commissure	406			Rhombencephalon
Cochlear decussation	407			Rhombencephalon
Decussation of the solitary tract	408			Rhombencephalon
Pineal gland	601			
Pituitary gland	602			
Ventricular system	701			